

Reproducibility study: Top-k Influential Nodes in social networks: A Game Perspective

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we are going to examine a simulation study published by [3] with respect to reproducibility. We will aim to obtain identical results by using an experiment design setup that resembles the original as closely as possible using the provided source code for their implementation. In addition we recreated the naive algorithms mentioned in the paper. Furthermore, we will look into the way the original authors analyzed their findings and we will run additional statistical tests. We conclude that we were able to reproduce several settings very accurately. For some other settings though, this task proved difficult due to missing documentation regarding calculation of the influence in the code for the original paper.

KEYWORDS

graph theory, influence maximization, social networks, viral marketing, experiment design, reproducibility

1 INTRODUCTION

In [3] the authors study a practical application with the aim of exerting influence of a new product by handing out samples to certain powerful "influencers" who then spread product adoption across the common network. This scenario is formally modelled in a graph $\mathcal{G}(V, E)$ where we seek to find a set $V' \subset V$, $|V'| = n$ such that the influence score of V' after a fixed amount of iterations t is maximized. This simulation can be broken down into two phases. In the first phase we seek to predict the most influential subset of the vertices. In the second step an influence score is calculated for the selected node set V' .

Independent variables of this simulation include the algorithm to predict the vertex subset V' with the highest influence score, the cardinality of the initial subset, a threshold that determines how much influence is required for a given node to convert as well as the data set on which the simulation is run. The dependent variables of interest include an influence score according to some calculation method and runtimes for finding the initial node set and/or calculating the influence.

The initial node set can be predicted using an algorithm labelled Greedy++ or Greedy. As the label already suggests the authors use a greedy approach to find this subset as the actual problem is NP hard and one has to resort to heuristics for any input data of relevant magnitude. The Greedy++ approach differs from Greedy solely in its implementation and turned out to be significantly more efficient in computing the initial node set. This approach was then compared with baselines such as choosing the initial nodes according to the highest page rank or out degree. Finally, we also hope to reproduce the effects of choosing this node set randomly.

One can also define a threshold $t \in [0, 1]$, such that the ratio r of adjacent active nodes to overall adjacent nodes for a given

Table 1: Thresholds that may define when a node "converts"

threshold	limit
linear	t
concave	t^2
convex	\sqrt{t}
majority vote	0.5

node v must exceed t for v to convert. In the simulation numbers u are sampled randomly from a uniform distribution on $[0, 1]$ (linear threshold). In the concave (convex) threshold t is then set to u^2 (\sqrt{u}). For majority voting t is fixed at 0.5.

Finally it is also interesting to study the effect of cardinality of V' as well as the effect of the input graph data. For the purposes of studying the simulation based on different data the authors included their data sets labelled NetHEPT, NetPhy and Epinions in a public GitHub repository¹. The edges in the Epinions data set had to be reversed manually as documented. The original paper contains a link to this repository.

2 STRATEGIES

We started out by cloning the GitHub repository using a link provided in the original paper.² Then we applied the steps outlined in the readme file of the repository to build executable files and run the simulation based on the provided data sets. This approach already worked quite well out of the box for the Greedy++ approach in step 1. However we were not able to find any implementation for the remaining algorithms (Greedy, Pagerank, Degree, Random), so we devised our own implementation for these cases. All algorithms that we implemented are based on the networkx library for graph manipulation. [2] The source file relevant here is named `find_init_nodes.py`. The greedy algorithm is implemented in the `greedy.py` file. As the implementation is done in Python and the original paper mentions a performance difference of three orders of magnitude between Greedy and Greedy++, we decided to not run the Greedy algorithm in experiments. Furthermore we had to tweak the existing implementation for Greedy++ slightly such that it would become easy to define a specific threshold model as command line parameter. The implementation can be run under MacOS (Catalina 10.15.7, processor 3.3 GHz Dual-Core Intel Core i5, RAM: 16 GB 2133 MHz LPDDR3).

We proceeded to create a Python pipeline (`experiment.py`) where we just invoke the existing executable files to find an ideal node subset for maximum influence spread and to calculate the

¹<https://github.com/yuzhimanhua/Influence-Maximization>

²Link to our own repository: https://github.com/mfm92/Reproducibility_TopK

actual influence score of that set. The script also takes care of running the same simulation for all seed set sizes between 1 and 20 to compare our results with the ones obtained in the original paper. The pipeline writes the combination of obtained seed set sizes, influence score and run time to a csv-file with a name that is unique to the parameter combination (data set/algorithm/threshold).

Finally we came up with an implementation to create a visualization of our findings and to run some statistical tests for the purposes of exploratory hypothesis checking (`stats_text.ipynb`). We extracted the results of the original paper and use a *t*-test for comparison with our own findings.

3 DIFFICULTIES

A variety of information that is crucial for the purposes of rerunning an experiment in exactly the same way was missing. Most prominently there was no documentation regarding the random seed and hardware used to obtain the original results. Due to the size of the networks we suspect that the influence of the randomness is somewhat decreased and comparable results can be found regardless. However, the most challenging hurdle in our opinion is the existence of various implementations for finding the node set predicted to be the most influential and calculating the influence score. These implementations serve the same purpose and are therefore related yet sometimes differing in crucial details. There is no indication in the original paper as to which version of those implementations to use. While this did not stop us from reproducing the results of the original paper in terms of relative performance of the algorithms it was quite hard to obtain the exact same absolute influence scores.

Due to the large run time of the concave threshold with NetHEPT, these results were not reproduced. All other algorithm-data combinations in the paper were tested.

Finally, we were able to reproduce largely the same absolute values on all settings. To this end we had to use file `Calc_Inf_LT.cpp` and apply some modifications in the threshold step to calculate influence scores. This contradicts with the suggestion from the original repository to use file `Calc_Inf.cpp` for obtaining influence scores.

4 KEY FINDINGS

The results for the Greedy++ algorithm closely match the published results, except for the Epinions data where the result differ for all implementations. All other settings were tested and compared to the published results.

Our implementations of the Degree, PageRank and Random algorithms perform quite differently from the reported numbers in the paper. Most notably the concave and convex thresholds were affected. Also the Epinions results could also not be replicated with these algorithms. The paper mentions that all edges are reverted for this data set which we also implemented.

5 CONCLUSION ABOUT THE EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Overall we would consider the experimental design setup to be quite solid. As mentioned previously though, the authors did not

document the randomization of their runs, nor which implementation to use (`Calc_Inf` vs. `Calc_Inf_IC` vs. `Calc_Inf_LT`). We tested all of the implementations and found that `Calc_Inf_IC` produced the most accurate results and concluded that this was the implementation used by the authors. The comparison of algorithm models in terms of influence and efficiency also proceeded without any formal statistical tests. Therefore we came up with our own tests in this reproducibility study. Finally we were unable to find any hints regarding the hardware used or the provenance of the data sets.

6 RESULTS

For all tested algorithms the results are very similar to the published results. To obtain the reference results, *WebPlotDigitizer* [1] was used with manual point entry. Our results were plotted with the digitized reference results shown as dashed lines. A two-sided t-test was used to interpret the difference in the residuals, since only 21 data points are available. It was assumed that random errors follow a $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$ distribution so a t-distribution with 20 degrees of freedom could be used to test the mean. Therefore the null hypothesis is given by $H_0 : \mu = 0$ and the alternative hypothesis for the two-tailed statistic is $H_1 : \mu \neq 0$.

The other algorithms sometimes show large differences in the calculated influence. We could not explain the reason for these errors, but it could be due to implementation differences. For the Degree and PageRank algorithms, the paper only states in a single sentence how these algorithms determine the most influential nodes. We implemented these to the best of our knowledge.

The running times also are correct in relation to the reported results as can be seen in figures 1 and 2. As you can see, the Greedy++ implementation took considerably longer than the naive implementations - for NetHept and NetPhy. However, due to different platforms these cannot be directly compared.

Figure 1: Run times of NetHept data with linear threshold. The Greedy++ implementation took considerably longer than the naive implementations.

The figures 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 show the comparisons of our results with the ones of the original paper. As mentioned above, our null hypothesis is that our results do not significantly differ from the original ones.

Algorithm	Runtime in s
Random	0.53
Degree	0.55
PageRank	1.83
Greedy++	32.30

Table 2: Tabular results for the run times for the NetHept data with linear threshold.

Figure 2: Run times of NetPhy data with linear threshold. The run times were similar to the NetHept data.

Algorithm	Runtime in s
Random	1.08
Degree	1.04
PageRank	5.45
Greedy++	80.24

Table 3: Tabular results for the run times for the NetPhy data with linear threshold.

6.1 NetHept with linear threshold

Figure 3: The results of the NetHept data with linear threshold.

For the NetHept data with linear threshold, all algorithms very closely follow the published results, as can be seen in figure 3. Also, the statistical tests for the Greedy++ implementation reinforce this notion. The p-value of the t-test is 0.4098, so the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

6.2 NetHept with convex threshold

Figure 4: The results of the NetHept data with convex threshold.

The results for the convex threshold are not so clear with significant deviations for the naive algorithms. While the results for the Greedy++ implementation are nearly identical with the published results in figure 4, the test still suggests the residuals are not random. The p-value of the t-test is 0.0029, so the null hypothesis has to be rejected. However, the mean absolute error of the residuals is only 0.89 so the results may have been influenced by the digitization. A look on the graph makes this also evident.

6.3 NetHept with majority threshold

Figure 5: The results of the NetHept data with majority threshold.

Again, the naive algorithms show very different trends compared to the published results and again the Greedy++ results are nearly

identical to the original paper. Here the test also fails with a p-value of the t-test of 0.0005 and the null hypothesis has to be rejected. However, the *mean absolute error* of the residuals is only 1.32 so the results may have been influenced by the digitization as before.

6.4 NetPhy with linear threshold

Figure 6: The results of the NetPhy data with linear threshold.

These results are better across all algorithms and the results have all equal trends, which figure 6 shows. The statistical test suggest the same for the Greedy++ implementation. The p-value of the t-test is 0.1970 so the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

6.5 Epinions with linear threshold

Figure 7: The results of the Epinions data with linear threshold. The p-value of the t-test is 0.0026 so the null hypothesis has to be rejected. Here, the mean absolute error of the residuals is rather high with a value of 403.00.

The results for the Epinions data are special in the regard that all algorithms show distinct deviations from the published results. Only the random algorithm closely follows its reference, as can be seen in figure 7. We tried other implementations of the influence calculations but to no avail.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The lack of transparency regarding the setup required for exact reproducibility of the original authors’ findings made it moderately challenging to run the simulation for all relevant parameter combinations. As a consequence of this we were faced with the question whether or not the findings in the original paper were to be fully trusted.

On the other hand the authors provided the scientific community with a code repository containing program sources and all relevant data sets. In our initial exploratory search of the proceedings mentioned in the first chapter this was seldom the case.

We remain with our personal opinion that the authors have chosen a very interesting topic with some potentially very fruitful applications in marketing and epidemiology, amongst others.

8 APPENDIX

The link to our repository: https://github.com/mfm92/Reproducibility_TopK

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